

Arylthallium-bis(trichloroacetates) and their Molecular Adducts

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Arylthallium-bis(trichloroacetates) have been shown to be either dimeric or polymeric in the solid state with two types of trichloroacetate groups, one of which is bridging bidentate and the other a weakly bonded terminal group. Reaction of $\text{RTl}(\text{O}_2\text{CCCl}_3)_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{Ph}$ or *p*-tolyl) with Lewis bases(L) has yielded new molecular adducts containing four- or five-coordinated thallium atom with both unidentate trichloroacetate groups.

RECENTLY¹ $\text{RTl}(\text{O}_2\text{CCCl}_3)_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{Ph}$ or *p*-tolyl) is reported to have been prepared by the direct thallation of the corresponding hydrocarbon with Tl_2O_3 and CCl_3COOH . Dethallation reactions of the compounds have been used for the preparation of many organic derivatives, but the mode of bonding of the trichloroacetate groups has not been examined. The present investigation reports the nature of bonding in the compounds and the preparation of their molecular adducts with various bases, such as 2-methylimidazole (2-Me-idz), 2,2'-dipyridyl (Dipy), tetramethyl ethylenediamine (TMEN), dimethyl acetamide (DMA), triphenylphosphineoxide (TPPO) and thiourea (TU).

Experimental

Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) (B.D.H.) was used after drying in vacuum. Phenyl- and *p*-tolyl-thallium-bis(trichloroacetates) were prepared by the reported method¹. Of the Lewis bases (Alfa Inorganics/Aldrich), the liquid bases were distilled before use and the solids recrystallised from suitable solvents. Solvents used were dried by standard methods. Physicochemical measurements were made as described earlier². All operations were carried out under dry nitrogen using conventional ground glass apparatus with interchangeable joints.

Preparation of adducts: The molecular adducts were prepared by the direct interaction of $\text{RTl}(\text{O}_2\text{CCCl}_3)_2$ with Lewis bases in refluxing acetone.

In a representative experiment, a solution of TMEN (1.16 g, 10 mmol) in acetone (~10 ml) was slowly added with stirring to a solution of $\text{PhTl}(\text{O}_2\text{CCCl}_3)_2$ (3.03 g, 5 mmol) in 20 ml of the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed for ~4 h. The excess of the solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. On standing in a deep freeze, a crystalline white product appeared. It was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and dried in vacuum. In some cases, where the product did

not separate on cooling, it was precipitated by addition of excess of petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and dried in vacuum. The analytical data of the adducts are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR $\text{RTl}(\text{O}_2\text{CCCl}_3)_2 \cdot \text{L}$

R	L	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		
			Tl*	O	H
Ph	2-Me-idz	186	29.41	24.14	1.40
			(29.68)	(24.40)	(1.59)
Ph	Dipy	231 d	26.58	31.11	1.52
			(26.80)	(31.80)	(1.70)
Ph	TMEN	192 d	28.12	26.06	2.78
			(28.29)	(26.30)	(2.90)
Ph	DMA	242	29.23	24.02	1.96
			(29.47)	(24.28)	(2.08)
Ph	TPPO	178	22.89	37.73	2.06
			(23.10)	(37.99)	(2.26)
Ph	TU	208	29.72	19.13	1.12
			(29.95)	(19.34)	(1.31)
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	2-Me-idz	172 d	28.86	25.36	1.71
			(29.09)	(25.62)	(1.85)
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	TPPO	221	22.56	38.39	2.21
			(22.74)	(38.73)	(2.44)
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	TU	191	29.11	20.42	1.98
			(29.33)	(20.68)	(1.58)

* Determined gravimetrically as Tl_2O_3 .

Results and Discussion

The data (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 1 (metal-base) stoichiometry of the adducts. The adducts are stable at room temperature and are insensitive towards atmospheric oxygen and moisture. They are sharp melting solids, white to light brown in colour and are soluble in organic solvents of high dielectric constant. The molar conductance of $\text{RTl}(\text{O}_2\text{CCCl}_3)_2$ (10^{-3} M in acetone) is 65.30 ± 3.06 and that of the adducts in the range $7.42\text{-}16.32 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$. The values show that $\text{RTl}(\text{O}_2\text{CCCl}_3)_2$ are appreciably ionised in acetone but the adducts are non-electrolytes. The molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in freezing nitrobenzene using a Beckmann thermometer of $\pm 0.01^\circ$ accuracy. The data support appreciable ionisation of RTl -

(O₂CCl₃)₂ and undissociated monomeric nature of the adducts in solution.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of RTl(O₂CCl₃)₂ and their adducts were recorded in the region 4000-650 cm⁻¹ in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrometer.

The assignments to absorptions due to the trichloroacetate groups were made on the basis of the reported⁸ spectrum of NaOCOCCl₃. In RTl(O₂CCl₃)₂, ν_{as} OCO and ν_s OCO appear as doublets at (1663±3, 1617±3) and (1361±1, 1337±3) cm⁻¹, respectively. The absorptions at 1617±3 and 1361±1 having a difference Δν_{OCO} 256±3 cm⁻¹ correspond to a bridging trichloroacetate group^{4,5}. The other absorptions at 1663±3 and 1337±3 having a difference Δν_{OCO} 332 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of an ionic terminal OOCOCCl₃ group⁸. RTl(O₂CCl₃)₂ are either dimeric or polymeric in the solid state having one bridging bidentate trichloroacetate group and the other weakly bonded terminal group. The appearance of ν_{C-C} and ν_{as} CCl₃ at 936±6 and 828±2 cm⁻¹, respectively, in the spectra of RTl(O₂CCl₃)₂ as doublets also show the presence of two types of trichloroacetate groups. The high molar conductance in acetone supports the presence of a weakly bonded ionic (terminal) group.

In the spectra of molecular adducts the ν_{as} OCO and ν_s OCO appear as singlets at 1680±5 and 1235±5 cm⁻¹, respectively, where both trichloroacetate groups are equivalent. The difference between the two modes of vibration (Δν_{OCO} 448±8 cm⁻¹) corresponds to an unidentate trichloroacetate group⁶⁻⁸. The appearance of ν_{C-C} and ν_{CCl₃} as singlets and the low value of molar conductance are in support of the conclusion. A comparison of the absorption of diagnostic value in the free Lewis bases with those in corresponding adducts indicate the presence of coordinated bases.

Pmr spectra: The pmr spectra of the adducts, PhTl(O₂CCl₃)₂.L (L=2-Me-idz or TMEN) were recorded in a mixture of CDCl₃ and DMSO-d₆ (2 drops) on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal standard.

In the pmr spectrum of 2-Me-idz¹⁵, the methyl protons appear at δ 2.42 and the two CH protons at 7.14. In the adduct, these resonances suffer up-field shifts and appear as singlets at δ 2.36 and 7.02, respectively, which may be due to the shielding

of ligand protons by the Lewis acid molecule. A multiplet centered at δ 7.31 is due to the phenyl protons of PhTl(O₂CCl₃)₂ molecule.

In the pmr spectrum of PhTl(O₂CCl₃)₂.TMEN, singlets appearing at δ 2.42 and 2.66 are due to the CH₃ and CH₂ protons respectively of TMEN molecule. The equivalence of CH₃ protons is attributed to the free rotation about the C-N bond⁷. A multiplet centered at δ 7.23 is assigned to phenyl group protons of PhTl(O₂CCl₃)₂. The integration of peaks are consistent with the proposed 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry of the adducts. It is suggested that the geometry around the thallium atom in molecular adducts of unidentate bases is tetrahedral and trigonal bipyramidal with bidentate bases.

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